

DIVERFARMING

Crop diversification and low-input farming across Europe: from practitioners' engagement and ecosystems services to increased revenues and value chain organisation

Distribution maps for thematic variables and territorial data to provide a decision support system for policy makers and planners

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Executive summary

The effect of diversification in the soil-plant-atmosphere system can be assessed at different scales, and the field represents the first assessment level. To this end, measured point or modelled data need to be generalised to the field to which they belong. In this project, selected physicochemical top- and sub-soil data measured at the beginning and at the end of the experiment were mapped at field scale, together with relevant previously defined indicators. But, much more than single variables, the variation that such variables have over time is the crucial aspect for understanding the effect of diversification. The maps of variables' change during the experiment (three years) represent the basis for the assessment of the effect of diversification on land productivity and the soil-plant system at field scale. Then a procedure for upscaling the data from field to landscape scale was set up and tested, first in two experimental areas, then applied to all the project areas. Finally, a method for cross-scale evaluation has been set up, tested and applied at landscape level in all the Countries participating to the project. The proposed methodology represents an useful and user-friendly instrument to support decisions for policy makers and planners.

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1. Introduction

Diversification indicates the farming practices that exploit functional biodiversity at multiple spatial and/or temporal scales. This include adding one or more crops into an existing rotation, but encompasses also the reduction of external inputs. Nicholls et al. (2016) confirm that crop diversification through rotation, intercropping and multiple cropping favours ecological interactions that contribute to maintain soil fertility, nutrient cycling and retention, water storage, pest/disease control and pollination, to reduce the use of external inputs, and to mitigate the effects of and adaptation to climate change. The adoption of crop diversification in intensive agricultural systems represents an important step towards sustainability.

The H2020 Diverfarming project (DF) was developed to empower stakeholders, in particular farmers, to implement low-input innovative practices of crop diversification. The project promotes the diversification and the reduction of inputs in the European farming systems, by proposing adequate agronomic solutions and by removing technical, social and economic barriers. A key step for the promotion of the diversified systems is the stakeholders' awareness of the diversification effect in comparison with more conventional systems.

The assessment of the effect of diversification versus the conventional crop management is challenging because many factors need to be considered at the same time and often the output of research projects are not readily understandable by farmers, advisors and policy makers. In DF, the overall assessment of diversification followed three synergistic approaches: modelling, application of geographic information systems (GIS) to analyse and represent modelled and measured data, and the use of appropriate indicators to assess the agroecosystem quality prior and after the application of the diversification strategies. Here the results of the GIS application are presented.

In assessing how diversified cropping systems influence soil-water-atmosphere systems, field scale evaluation is the first step. Measured point data, or modelled ones, need to be generalized to the field to which they belong, to have a comprehensive view of the effect of crop diversification on farm yields, soil, and environment. Thus, data collection and map production for subsequent multi-scale assessment was implemented.

Agricultural and environmental managers often require spatial continuous data over a region of interest to make effective and informed decisions, and scientists need accurate data which are well-distributed across a region to make justified interpretations. However, spatial distribution data of agriculture are often collected from point sources. Therefore, spatial interpolation techniques are essential for estimating biophysical variables in unsampled locations. Interpolation is the procedure of estimating the value of properties at unsampled points or areas using a limited number of sampled observations.

Recently, the availability and accessibility of GIS, Global Positioning Systems (GPS), topographic data derived from Digital Elevation Models (DEMs), predictive or inference models, and software for data analysis have greatly advanced the art of upscaling information from farm to landscape level. Incorporation of auxiliary data often allows to reduce the estimation error when performing an

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interpolation of measured/modelled data over a broader territory, thereby improving our understanding of interactions among landscape features.

The present deliverable illustrates the methodologies followed for the assessment of crop diversification effects at field and landscape level and shows the results of evaluation of some indicators at present time and in the next 30 years – including the projected climate change - for the different case studies/long term experiments (CSs/LTs) studied in the project, based on data availability.

2. Materials and Methods for mapping

The mapping phase of DF was conducted at two different levels: field scale and landscape scale, and the two different scales required different input data and different mapping methods (Figure 1). Moreover, several preliminary activities were carried out, including the collection, homogenisation and standardisation of data coming from measurement in WP5, and the harmonisation of the model outputs. Geostatistical interpolation and GIS implementation were the methods selected for the evaluation of diversification effects both at field and at landscape level. The variation between the final situation and the initial one was considered for the assessment.

Figure 1. Scheme of multiscale analysis in Diverfarming

The produced maps represent the basis for the assessment of the effect of diversification on land productivity and the soil-plant system at different scales.

2.1. Materials

In evaluating a territory, data must be georeferenced, and have different resolution depending on the required precision of the assessment - field or landscape level. In DF the following data were collected: agro-climatic data, soil data, land-use data, DF indicators data. Measured data from WP3-5, modelled data from WP7 Task 7.1 and 7.2 were used as a starting point for mapping.

This section provides an overview of the information collected from the DF CSs and LTs, as well as an initial analysis of such information. In Table 1 an overview of the data available from each experimental area is reported.

Table 1. Data available for each CS/LT (FL = field level; LL = landscape level)

CS/LT	Climate data	Soil profiles (FL)	Soil profiles (LL)	Soil maps (LL)	Detailed Land-use (LL)	Land-use (LL)	Indicators data (LL)
CS1	x	x		x	x	x	x
CS2	x	x		x	x	x	x
CS3a	x	x		x		x	x
CS3b	x	x		x		x	x
CS4	x	x				x	
CS5	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
CS6	x	x				x	x
CS7	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
CS7bis	x	x				x	
CS8	x	x				x	
CS9	x	x		x			x
CS10	x	x		x			x
CS11	x	x		x			x
CS12	x	x		x			x
CS13	x	x		x			x
CS14	x	x		x			
CS15	x	x					
CS16	x	x		x		x	x
LT1	x	x		x		x	x
LT2	x	x		x		x	x
LT3	x	x					
LT4	x	x		x		x	x
LT5	x	x		x		x	x

CS/LT	Climate data	Soil profiles (FL)	Soil profiles (LL)	Soil maps (LL)	Detailed Land-use (LL)	Land-use (LL)	Indicators data (LL)
LT8	x	x					
LT9	x	x		x		x	x

2.2. Methods and examples of application

2.2.1. First step: mapping at field level

Spatial interpolation is the procedure for estimating the value of properties at unsampled sites within an area covered by existing observations. Because of high cost and limited resources, data collection is usually conducted only in a limited number of selected point locations. Spatial interpolation is the process of using points with known values to estimate values at other unknown points. There are many interpolation methods that can be subdivided in deterministic and probabilistic ones. The most widely used deterministic method is the Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW), simple and readily available. It is based on the assumption that the value at an unsampled point can be approximated as a weighted average of values at points within a certain cut-off distance, or from a given number of the closest points (typically 10 to 30). Weights are usually inversely proportional to a power of distance (Burrough, 1986; Watson, 1992). Probabilistic methods are proper of Geostatistics, and are based on the assumption that spatially distributed objects are spatially correlated; in other words, things that are close together tend to have similar characteristics.

First, physico-chemical top- and sub-soil data measured at the beginning of the experiment (time zero, T_0) were mapped at field scale, together with some indicators defined in collaboration with Task 7.4. The estimated maps of measured point data at plot scale were drawn applying IDW interpolation method to the measured data at T_0 and to some indicators, both for topsoil and for subsoil up to the experimental fields' extent. It was previously verified that, given the small number of measured points and the generally limited spatial variability of the above-mentioned parameters, a deterministic interpolator like IDW can provide good spatial estimates with an acceptable global map error. In each map the colour scale was defined by natural breaks.

When the final experimental data became available, the maps of the final situation and of the variation of the measured parameters were produced. Exemplary maps of the initial and final C content, of the C variation and of the variation in C/N ratio for the 0-30 cm soil layer are reported below for CS7, set-up in the Po Valley, Cremona Province, Northern Italy.

Figure 2. CS7, Total Organic Carbon in the 0-30 cm layer at the beginning (a) and at the end (b) of the experiment.

Figure 3. CS7, Total Organic Carbon variation in the 0-30 cm layer (a); variation of the Carbon/Nitrogen ratio in the 0-30 cm layer (b).

Maps of modelled Total Organic Carbon (TOC) variation in the considered scenarios for the experimental field show how the diversification could mitigate the C loss from the soils in the area. This is clear also looking at the maps of modelled TOC variation in the landscape (Figure 6). Field maps as the one in Figure 3a show also that adopting crop diversification together with other conservative practices can be effective not only in mitigating soil C loss, but also in enhancing soil C sequestration.

2.2.2. Second step: mapping at landscape level

The assessment of agriculture at a landscape scale is necessary to better guide regional agricultural planning and can assist in setting priorities for more detailed monitoring of economic and environmental aspects of agriculture. Aiming to improve the contribution of agriculture to sustainable regional development, the assessment must take into account the location and the diversity of cropping systems

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(Chopin et al., 2017). Maps can help policymakers in identifying territorial impacts in terms of agro-environmental, social and economic effects. In particular, our interest was in assessing how diversified cropping systems influence soil-water-atmosphere systems in different pedoclimatic regions of Europe, and this will play an important role in the state-wide and regional evaluation of agricultural land status.

Switching from the field scale to landscape scale means lowering the geometric precision to achieve a broader sight of the territory. First of all, the support (landscape area of interest) was defined for each case study as a continuous area surrounding the experimental site with similar pedological and climatic features, and with the same management. The definition of the landscape extent was driven mainly by the Soil Region - an area across which soils are relatively uniform - to which the experimental field belongs, and by the Municipalities (NUTS3) interested in the DF diversifications.

A procedure for upscaling the data from field to landscape scale was set up and tested in the experimental areas that provided both measured and auxiliary data. Data for upscaling at landscape scale were collected from almost all the partners, then integrated with information from European databases where only few more detailed data were available.

In this study two different approaches based on the available data were applied: in areas where georeferenced soil profiles were available (high resolution data), a procedure for upscaling using a machine learning algorithm was set up; where only soil maps were available (coarse data), a “simplified” procedure using indicators was applied.

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Figure 4. Flowchart of the upscaling procedure.

Upscaling using a machine learning algorithm

First, the complete soil profiles available falling into the defined spatial framework for each area were chosen. Some soil profiles from the WoSIS database (<https://www.isric.org/explore/wosis>) were added, if relevant for the considered area. A set of 15 covariates (auxiliary information), described in Table 2, was used in the machine learning algorithm application. The covariates are selected based on their correlation degree, and then converted to principal components to reduce covariance and dimensionality, and also to fill in all missing pixels. The resulting principal components are related with the target variable by means of the ‘ranger’ function, a fast implementation of Random Forests, particularly suited for high dimensional data. The output is a prediction map with an associated error map.

Table 2. Covariates used for Machine learning

Predictor	Description	Reference
DEM	Digital elevation model, 25 m	https://land.copernicus.eu/user-corner/publications/eu-dem-flyer/at_download/file
CPROF	Profile curvature	Olaya (2006)

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Predictor	Description	Reference
DEVMEAN	Deviation from the mean value – Relations of each grid cell to its neighbourhood	Wilson and Gallant (2000)
OPENN, OPENP	Topographic openness, expresses the dominance (positive) or enclosure (negative) of a landscape location. Openness has been related to how wide a landscape can be viewed from any position	Anders et al. (2009) Prima et al. (2006) Yokoyama et al. (2002)
SLOPE	Slope	Olaya (2006)
TWI	The 'SAGA Wetness Index' is similar to the 'Topographic Wetness Index', but it is based on a modified catchment area calculation which does not think of the flow as very thin film. It predicts for cells situated in valley floors with a small vertical distance to a channel a more realistic, higher potential soil moisture compared to the standard TWI calculation	Boehner et al. (2002) Boehner and Selige (2006)
VBF	Combination of a 'multiresolution index of valley bottom flatness' (MRVBF) and the complementary 'multiresolution index of the ridge top flatness' (MRRTF)	Gallant and Dowling (2003)
VDEPTH	Valley depth, calculated as the difference between the elevation and an interpolated ridge level	Olaya (2006)
NIR	Landsat8 OLI band 4, 30 m	Hansen et al. (2013)
RED	Landsat8 OLI band 3, 30 m	Hansen et al. (2013)
SW1	Landsat8 OLI band 5, 30 m	Hansen et al. (2013)
SW2	Landsat8 OLI band 7, 30 m	Hansen et al. (2013)
TREECOVER	Tree cover in the year 2000, defined as canopy closure for all vegetation taller than 5 m in height, 30 m	Hansen et al. (2013)
BARESOIL	Global bare ground cover derived from annual seamless composites of Landsat 7 ETM+ per band – median reflectance values of all cloud/shadow free growing season observations, 30 m	Hansen et al. (2013)

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The upscaling procedure was applied to the CSs and LTs, in order to test the procedure itself and to produce the maps. As an example, in CS7 a convenient set of information was available. Two crop management scenarios with and without diversification options were investigated: currently a tomato–durum wheat rotation is adopted, in which a leguminous crop (pea for food) was introduced followed by tomato as second crop. A set of 24 soil point samples was collected in this field from the 0–30 cm layer. The model ECOSSE, modified to simultaneously run in several spatially distributed points (MULTIECOSSE), was used to predict TOC change in soils after 30 years of diversification and of conventional farming. The model was first run in point soil profiles, then the variation of TOC after 30 years in each measured point was spatialised with IDW to better visualise the effect of crop diversification. The same simulation was carried out in a set of soil profiles with the same land use (arable crop) in a quite homogeneous landscape area. Finally, an interpolation at landscape scale was performed (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Schematic view of the procedure followed for long-term prediction of the effect of diversification.

In figure 6, the maps of simulated TOC in the 0–30 cm layer for CS7 at landscape scale, both for conventional and diversified management, are shown.

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Figure 6. CS7, Total Organic Carbon variation from 2018 to 2047 in conventional scenario (a) and in diversified scenario (b) at landscape scale.

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In this case the proposed procedure, bringing together a model for simulating C dynamics, an interpolation method to extend the results to the field extent, and a machine learning approach to upscale the model results to a broader landscape, has proven to be effective in highlighting the effect of crop diversification with legumes on soil C loss in the long term at different scales.

Simplified upscaling using soil and land-use maps

Since in most of the studied areas data from complete soil profiles are lacking, a “simplified” upscaling method of DF results was adopted, to evaluate all the project areas. The information considered for this study is mainly about climate, soil and crops. Wider landscape areas with the same crops and the same climatic and pedological characteristics were considered in the study. In some cases the administrative boundaries were adopted as mapping limits, in other cases the boundaries of the landscape were defined together with the partners who better knew their territory. For each area the climate was assumed to be the same of the correspondent CS/LT.

CORINE Land Cover (CLC, <https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/corine-land-cover/clc2018>) was used as land use all over Europe, except for Italy, where a more detailed land use map was available and was used (“Banca dati dell'uso e copertura del suolo – DUSAF”). This land use map is based on the CLC classification, so that the cartographic legend is the same for all the DF areas for an easier comparison. Into the selected landscape area, for each CS/LT only the land use categories to which it belongs were considered (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Detail of the CORINE Land Cover (CLC) map with the position of the Case Study n.11 in Hungary. In CS11 the crop is a vineyard, corresponding to the class “221: Vineyards” of CLC. Other CLC classes in the figure: 112: Urban; 311: Broad-leaved forest; 321: Natural grassland; 324: Transitional woodland/shrub; 211: Non-irrigated arable land; 243: Land principally occupied by agriculture with significant areas of natural vegetation; 512: Water bodies.

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Soil data were derived from soil maps, since detailed soil profiles were not available. The point representing each CS/LT was associated to the reference soil profile of the correspondent map unit, and then the same map unit was considered into the landscape area (Table 3). Where more detailed soil maps were available, these latter were used - even if this caused a lack of homogeneity among the partner Countries, the detail information was preferred with respect to the geometric scale.

In each area, overlaying the soil and the land use maps some polygons were obtained with the same characteristics of the CSs/LTs analysed in DF (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Landscape map of the Italian area. In purple the zones with the same soil and land-use of CS5, in light blue the areas with the same soil and land-use of CS7. The yellow dots represent the location of the case studies. The green line represents the administrative boundaries of Mantua, Cremona and Brescia provinces (Lombardy Region).

Table 3 Soil and land use data, sources and landscape boundaries used for mapping at landscape level

CS/LT	Country	Soil type	Soil data source	Land use (CLC code)	Land use data source	Landscape boundaries
CS1	Spain	Calcaric regosols	LUCDEME –	222 Fruits trees and berry plantations	CORINE land cover	Municipality of Murcia and surroundings

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CS/LT	Country	Soil type	Soil data source	Land use (CLC code)	Land use data source	Landscape boundaries
			Murcia ¹		2018 ²	
CS2	Spain	Calcaric regosols	LUCDEME – Murcia	222 Fruits trees and berry plantations	CORINE land cover 2018	Municipality of Murcia and surroundings
CS16	Spain	Calcic xerosols	LUCDEME – Murcia	212 Permanently irrigated land	CORINE land cover 2018	Municipality of Murcia and surroundings
LT1	Spain	Calcic xerosols	LUCDEME – Murcia	212 Permanently irrigated land	CORINE land cover 2018	Municipality of Murcia and surroundings
LT3	Spain	Haplic calcisols	Soil Regions ³ of the European Union and Adjacent Countries	242 Complex cultivation patterns	CORINE land cover 2018	Municipality of Lorca and surroundings
LT4	Spain	Haplic gypsisols	Soil Regions of the European Union and Adjacent Countries	243 Land principally occupied by agriculture, with significant areas of natural vegetation	CORINE land cover 2018	Municipalities of Huesca, Zaragoza and surroundings + other areas with the same soil type
CS3a	Spain	Haplic gypsisols	Soil Regions of the European Union and Adjacent Countries	211 Non irrigated arable land	CORINE land cover 2018	Municipalities of Huesca, Zaragoza and surroundings + other areas with the same soil type
CS3b	Spain	Haplic gypsisols	Soil Regions of the European Union and Adjacent Countries	212 Permanently irrigated land	CORINE land cover 2018	Municipalities of Huesca, Zaragoza and surroundings + other areas with the same soil type
CS5	Italy	Luvissols	Lombardia	211 Non irrigated arable land	Database	Cremona, Mantua and Brescia provinces

¹ LUCDEME - URL: <https://directory.spatineo.com/service/20582>

² CORINE Land Cover 2018 -URL: <https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/corine-land-cover/clc2018>

³ Soil Regions of the European Union and Adjacent Countries 1:5,000,000 (WMS) URL: <https://produktcenter.bgr.de/terraCatalog/Query/Detail.do?fileIdentifier=AE71FFEE-1AE9-4624-AE3F->

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CS/LT	Country	Soil type	Soil data source	Land use (CLC code)	Land use data source	Landscape boundaries
			Region ⁴		DUSAF ⁵	
CS7	Italy	Calcisols	Lombardia Region	211 Non irrigated arable land	Database DUSAF	Cremona, Mantua and Brescia provinces
CS11	Hungary	Lamellic arenosols	Soil Regions of the European Union and Adjacent Countries	221 Vineyards	CORINE land cover 2018	NUTS Level 3 Baranya
LT9	Hungary	Lamellic arenosols	Soil Regions of the European Union and Adjacent Countries	221 Vineyards	CORINE land cover 2018	NUTS Level 3 Baranya
CS12	Finland	Haplic cambisols	Soil Regions of the European Union and Adjacent Countries	211 Non irrigated arable land	CORINE land cover 2018	NUTS Level 3 Kanta-Häme
CS13	Finland	Haplic podzols	Soil Regions of the European Union and Adjacent Countries	211 Non irrigated arable land	CORINE land cover 2018	NUTS level 3 Keski-Pohjanmaa
CS9	Germany	Haplic cambisols	Soil Regions of the European Union and Adjacent Countries	221 Vineyards	CORINE land cover 2018	NUTS Level 3 Rheinland-Pfalz

Data collected in WP4 and WP5 were used to compile a set of indicators for evaluating the effects of diversification in all the CSs and LTs. Such indicators, grouped in 5 classes (Soil, Land, Biodiversity, Greenhouse gas emissions and Economic evaluation), are: Bulk density, Soil carbon (current and predicted for the next 30 years), Total nitrogen, Carbon-Nitrogen ratio, Phosphorus availability in soil, Exchangeable Potassium, Calcium and Magnesium, Copper in soil, Soil Micronutrients (Fe, Mn, Zn), Available inorganic mineral contaminants, Soil acidity (pH), Soil available water capacity, Cover crop, Erosion index, Bacteria biodiversity, Bacteria diversity in soil, Earthworm biodiversity, CO₂ emissions in the next 30 years, Nitrous oxide emissions in the next 30 years, Total costs and Crop Gross Margin.

⁴ Regione Lombardia – Basi informative dei suoli URL:

https://www.geoportale.regione.lombardia.it/metadati?p_p_id=detailSheetMetadadata_WAR_gptmetadadataportlet&p_p_lifecycle=0&p_p_state=normal&p_p_mode=view&_detailSheetMetadadata_WAR_gptmetadadataportlet_uid=%7BA7138B8A-9025-4802-82BC-52267B60A3D7%7D

⁵ Banca dati dell'uso e copertura del suolo (DUSAF) <https://www.dati.lombardia.it/Territorio/Dusaf-6-0-Usa-del-suolo-2018/7rae-fng6>

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The detailed definition of the indicators is described in the deliverable D7.1 (http://www.diverfarming.eu/images/deliverables/D7_1.pdf).

All the indicators were calculated both at the beginning and at the end of the experiment, for the conventional management as well as for the different diversification strategies applied to each CS/LT. For each indicator, the variation from the starting period to the final one was calculated (Δ), then the differences between the two management options allowed to evaluate if there was an improvement, a worsening or an unchanged situation.

Since the final goal of this work was to support policy and decision makers, often simple numbers are not useful for stakeholders – especially if they are not experienced agronomists or pedologists. For this reason, indicators' value ranges were classified in 3 qualitative categories summarizing the relative variation between the initial and final values of each indicator: “worse”, “stable”, “improve” in comparison with the conventional management.

Therefore, overview indicators maps were built, in which each polygon has a land use and a soil type as the correspondent CSs/LTs, and an evaluation of a specific indicator for the diversified management compared with the conventional one.

3. Assessment of diversification effect

3.1. Assessment with field maps

Field maps can be a support to farmers and consultants to understand the response of crop management at field level. Different field maps of indicators based on spatial interpolation – which can be easily updated whenever new data become available - are useful to monitor the state of the soil-plant system in relation to the crop management adopted by the farmer. These maps can be considered as a tool to check the positive or negative impact of a specific crop diversification management on the field for each characteristic of the soil, e.g. the amount of TOC in the soil. If the effect of the soil-plant system in a portion of the field is not as the farmer expect, he can change some agronomic practice only in that sector, applying in this way a precision agriculture method. This can enhance the sustainability of farming, e.g. reducing inputs where they are not necessary.

As a matter of facts, a longer time might be necessary to measure the effect of diversification on soil properties; this should be taken into account in the evaluation of DF maps. For example, considering TOC we can observe that, from the beginning to the end of DF experiment:

- in CS1 (Spain – Murcia) almond intercropped with *Capparis spinosa* showed an improvement, while almond intercropped with *Thymus hyemalis* showed a worsening;
- in CS2 (Spain – Murcia) both mandarin with cover crops (reduced tillage) intercropped with vetch/barley and fava bean, and mandarin with cover crops (reduced tillage) intercropped with vetch/barley and fava bean (1st year), campion, purslane and cardoon (2nd year) and cowpea and rocket (3rd year) showed a worsening;
- in CS3a (Spain – Huesca-Zaragoza) barley monocropping with no-tillage and barley-wheat-pea rotation did not show significant change;

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- in CS3b (Spain – Huesca-Zaragoza) pea-maize multiple cropping showed an improvement, while barley-maize multiple cropping did not show significant change;
- in CS5 and CS7 (Italy) the rotation tomato-pea/tomato-wheat showed a worsening, while with the addition of digestate the situation changed depending on the soil type;
- in CS9 (Germany) both vineyards intercropped with oregano and with thymus showed an improvement;
- in CS11 (Hungary) vineyards intercropped with yarrow *Achillea millefolium* showed an improvement, while vineyards intercropped with native grass mix for fodder showed a worsening in most of the samples;
- in CS12 (Finland) barley with no-tillage and barley with no-tillage with 1 year of rapeseed did not show significant change, while barley monocrop in conventional tillage with 1 year of rapeseed showed an improvement;
- in CS13 (Finland) all the tested diversification options (barley-ley-ley-barley, barley-clovergrass-ley-vetch, barley-clovergrass-rye-oats) showed an improvement;
- in CS16 (Spain – Murcia) melon with cowpea, melon with mixed intercropping and melon with row intercropping 2:1 vegetable phase showed an improvement, while melon with row intercropping 1:1 vegetable phase did not show significant change;
- in LT1 (Spain – Murcia) melon in summer and leaf cabbage in winter (organic management) and melon in summer and leaf cabbage in winter (biodynamic) did not show significant change, while melon in summer and leaf cabbage in winter (biodynamic) showed an improvement;
- in LT3 (Spain – Murcia/Lorca) both almond monocrop with reduced tillage and almond intercropped with *Avena sativa* and *Vicia sativa* with reduced tillage did not show significant change;
- in LT4 (Spain – Huesca-Zaragoza) barley with no-tillage showed an improvement.

All the produced maps were uploaded on DF OneDrive WP7, task 7.3 folder and are available at https://diverfarming.sharepoint.com/:f:/s/wp7modelling/EnrTplEemy1Dur3tg-xha8gBYcrFnHp8zE69fW_tEgVk1Q?e=ErXLeE

3.2 Assessment with landscape maps

Table 4 shows the results of indicators evaluation at landscape level. These data can be a support to stakeholders to understand if the crop management diversification has a positive impact on soil, land, biodiversity and economic aspect in a territory or if some changing in techniques or different type of crops must be applied.

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Table 4 Results of all the indicators considered in DF. Green colour indicates a positive evaluation of diversification strategy compared with the conventional management, yellow indicates a stable situation, red indicates a worsening result. White cells correspond to “no data”. (Bd: Bulk density, C: Soil carbon content, C30: Soil carbon content next 30 years, Nt: total nitrogen, C/N: carbon-nitrogen ratio, Pav: Available phosphorus, K: potassium, Caex and Mgex: exchangeable calcium and magnesium, Cu: copper in soil, MNu: Soil Micronutrients (Fe,Mn, Zn), CONT: Available inorganic mineral contaminants, PH: acidity, AWC: Soil available water capacity, CVI: Cover crop, ER: erosion index, CHAO_BI: Chao index of bacteria biodiversity, SHA: Bacteria diversity in the soil (Shannon index), EW: earthworm biodiversity, EZ: soil enzyme activities, GHG_C: CO2 emissions in next 30 years, GHG_N: Nitrous oxide emissions in next 30 years , Cost: total costs , GM: Crop Gross Margin, I=improve, S=stable, W=worse, LE=lower erosion, HC= higher costs, LC= lower costs.)

Index class	Soil												Land		Biodiversity				Greenhouse Gas emissions		Economic evaluation			
	BD	C	C30	Nt	C/N	Pav	K	Caex	Mgex	Cu	MNu	CONT	PH	AWC	CVI	ER	CHAO_BI	SHA	EW	EZ	GHG_C	GHG_N	Cost	GM
CS1_2	S	I	I	S	S	S	I	I	I	S	S		S	I	I	LE	I	I			I	S		
CS1_3	S	I	I	S	S	S	I	I	I	S	S		S	I	I	LE	I	I			I	S	HC	S
CS10_2	S	I	I	I	S	I	S	S	S	S	S		S	I	I	S	W	S			W	W	S	S
CS10_3	W	S	I	S	I	I	S	I	I	S	S		S	I	I	S	W	S			W	W	S	S
CS11_2	S	I	I	I	S	S	S	I	S	S	S		S	S	I	LE	I	I			S	S	S	I
CS11_3	S	W	I	W	S	W	S	I	S	I	W		S	I	I	LE	I	I			I	S	S	I
CS12_2	S	S	W	S	S	S	S	S	S				S	S	S		I	S	I		W	W	S	S
CS12_3	I	I	W	S	I	S	S	W	S				S	S	I		I	S	I		I	S	S	S
CS12_4	I	S	W	W	I	W	W	W	S				S	S	I		I	S	I		I	I	S	S
CS13_1	S	I	W	I	I	I	W	S	I				S	S							I	I		
CS13_3	S	I	W	I	I	W	W	S	I				S	S							S	S		
CS13_4	S	I	W	I	I	W	S	S	I				S	S							S	S		
CS16_2	I	I	W	I	I	I	I	I	I	S	S		S	S			S	W	I		I	W		
CS16_3	I	I	I	I	I	W	I	I	W	S	S		S	S			S	W	S		W	S	HC	W
CS16_5	S	S	I	I	I	S	I	I	W	S	S		S	S			S	W	W		W	W	LC	W
CS16_7	S	I	I	I	I	I	I	I	W	S	S		S	S			S	W	I		W	W	LC	W
CS2_2	W	W	I	S	S	S	W	S	S	S	W		S	S	I	LE	W	W	S		S	S	HC	I
CS2_3	S	W	I	S	W	I	W	S	W	S	S		S	S	I	LE	S	W	S		S	W	S	I
CS3a_2	I	I	I	I	S	S	S	S	S				S	I	S						W	W	S	I
CS3a_3	I	S	I	S	S	W	S	S	S				S	W	I						I	W	S	I

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CS3b_4	S	S	S	W	S	W	W	I	S				S	W	I						W	W	HC	S
CS3b_7	S	S	S	W	W	W	W	S	S				S	W	I						W	W	HC	S
CS5_1	I	W	I	W	W	W	W	I	S	S	W	S	S	I	I					W	I	I	HC	I
CS5_3	S	W	I	W	W	I	I	I	W	S	I	S	S	I	I					S	I	I	HC	I
CS6_2	S	W	S	I	W	I	S		I	S	I	S	S	W	I					W	W	W	HC	I
CS6_1	S	W	S	I	W	I	W		I	S	I	S	S	W	I					W	W	W	HC	I
CS7_3	S	W	I	W	I	I	S	I	I	I	W	S	S	I	I					S	W	S	HC	S
CS7_4	S	W	W	W	I	I	I	I	I	I	W	S	S	I	I					I	W	S	HC	S
CS9_2	S	I	S	I	S	I	S	I	I	I			S	S	I	LE	I	S	I		S	S	S	S
CS9_3	S	I	S	I	S	W	W	W	S	I			S	S	I	S	I	S	I		S	S	S	S
LT1_2	S	S	I	I	S	I	I	S	S	S	S		S	S			W	S	W		S	S		
LT1_3	S	I	I	I	S	S	I	S	S	S	S		S	S			S	S	W		W	W		
LT2_1	S	S	I	I	I	I	I	I	S	W	I		S	S			S	S			I	S		
LT2_2	S	S	I	I	I	I	I	S	S	S	I		S	S			I	S			W	S		
LT2_4	S	I	S	I	I	S	S	I	S	S	I		S	S			S	S			W	S		
LT3_2		S	I														S	S			W	W		
LT3_3		S	I														S	S			W	W		
LT4_2	S	I	I	S	S	W	S	W	I				S	W			S	S			W	W		
LT5_2	S	I	S	I	S	W	S	S	I	W			S	S		LE	S	S	I		S	S		
LT9_2	S	I	I	S	I		W	W	S	I	S		S	S							S	S		
LT9_3	S	W		S	W		I	I	I	I	I		S	S										

DIVERFARMING

In the table, the “negative” results don’t mean that crop diversification has negative effects, but that in the specific case study the differences between the final and the initial value have a lesser value than the difference of those calculated in the conventional management conditions. The results are influenced by climate and soil characteristics, and where the results are not positive the new crops might need a longer time to adapt to the particular pedo-climatic conditions, or the chosen diversification option might need some adjustment to best fit such environmental conditions.

All the indicators’ maps elaborated at landscape scale represent an additional tool for stakeholder to understand how the application of different crop diversification management can influence a large region or a province or a geomorphological area. All the maps were built under two different scenarios: “present”, using the information about the current climate, and “30 years”, considering the modelled results in the next 30 years using projected climate obtained by the Agri4Cast platform (ETHZ, Intermediate realization of climate change with markedly different precipitations patterns). Such maps give at a glance a territorial overview to policy makers, useful to individuate the portion of territory where it is possible to apply the same diversifications used during DF and consequently have the same (positive) results identified and predicted in the CSs/LTs.

The following landscape maps were built for TOC indicator with the same climatic, soil and land use characteristics of DF experimental areas.

DIVERFARMING

Finland

Kanta-Häme region

Figure 9. Overview indicators maps for total organic carbon content of the Kanta- Häme region at present time (a) and in the next 30 years (b), where the diversification option barley with no-tillage as CS12 is applied.

DIVERFARMING

The maps in Figure 9 show the area - about 201 km² - in which considering the current land use as CS12 (rainfed conventional cereal monocropping), the same diversification could be applied: barley with no-tillage. In the present situation (3 years of experiment in DF) there was no significant change in TOC, while after 30 years of such management a worsening is foreseen by the model. In climate change situation, the option of barley with no tillage seems to be not sustainable in the long term. This result indicates that for diversification to be successful it is necessary to include modification in the management to improve the sustainability, by increasing the C inputs to soil - e.g. use of multicropping, cover crops or exogenous organic matter application.

The maps in figure 10 show the same area in which, considering the current land use as CS12, the same diversification could be applied: barley monocrop in conventional tillage and 1 year of rapeseed. In the present situation (3 years of experiment in DF) there was an improvement in TOC, while after 30 years of such management a worsening is foreseen by the model. This option seems to be sustainable in the immediate future under current climate but not in the long term. As for the previous diversification, the climatic change requires from the farmer an increased attention to improve the management.

The maps in figure 11 show the same area in which considering the current land use as CS12 the same diversification could be applied: barley with no-tillage and 1 year of rapeseed. In the present situation (3 years of experiment in DF) there was no significant change in TOC, while after 30 years of such management a worsening is foreseen by the model. This option seems to be not sustainable in the long term under climate change. As for the previous cases it is important for the farmers to revise carefully the management by increasing C inputs and reducing losses from the system.

DIVERFARMING

Figure 10. Overview indicators maps for total organic carbon content of the Kanta- Häme region at present time (a) and in the next 30 years (b), where the diversification option barley monocrop in conventional tillage and 1 year of rapeseed as CS12 is applied.

DIVERFARMING

Figure 11. Overview indicators maps for total organic carbon content of the Kanta- Häme region at present time (a) and in the next 30 years (b), where the diversification option barley with no-tillage and 1 year of rapeseed as CS12 is applied.

DIVERFARMING

Keski-Pohjanmaa region

Figure 12. Overview indicators maps for total organic carbon content of the Keski - Pohjanmaa region at present time (a) and in the next 30 years (b), where the diversification option feed for milk production (barley-ley-ley-barley) as CS13 is applied.

DIVERFARMING

The maps in figure 12 show the area - about 188 km² - in which considering the current land use as CS13 (rainfed conventional feed production) the same diversification could be applied: rotation barley-ley-ley-barley as feed for milk production. In the present situation (3 years of experiment in DF) under current climate, there was an increase of TOC, while after 30 years of such management a decrease of this parameter is foreseen by the model. As in the other cases, under future climate change conditions, this option seems to be less favourable than conventional system in the long term.

The maps in figure 13 show the same area with the current land use as CS13 in which the same diversification could be applied: rotation barley-clovergrass-ley-vetch with oat. In the present situation (3 years of experiment in DF) there was an improvement in TOC, while after 30 years of such management a worsening is foreseen by the model. This option seems to be sustainable in the current climate. In the long term, however, the diversification seems to perform worse than the conventional system.

The maps in figure 14 show the same area with the current land use as CS13 in which the same diversification could be applied: rotation barley-clovergrass-rye-oats. In the present situation (3 years of experiment in DF) there was an improvement in TOC, while after 30 years of such management a worsening is foreseen by the model in diversified system compared with conventional. Again, as in the other cases of Finland, the application of diversification implies an additional effort by farmers to improve the C budget, reducing losses and increasing the C sequestration.

DIVERFARMING

Figure 13. Overview indicators maps for total organic carbon content of the Keski - Pohjanmaa region at present time (a) and in the next 30 years (b), where the diversification option barley-clovergrass-ley-vetch with oat as CS13 is applied.

DIVERFARMING

Figure 14. Overview indicators maps for total organic carbon content of the Keski - Pohjanmaa region at present time (a) and in the next 30 years (b), where the diversification option barley-clovergrass-rye-oats as CS13 is applied.

DIVERFARMING

Germany

Rheinland-Pfalz region

Figure 15. Overview indicators maps for total organic carbon content of the Rheinland-Pfalz region at present time (a) and in the next 30 years (b), where the diversification option vineyards intercropped with oregano (planted) for multiple uses as CS9 is applied.

DIVERFARMING

The maps in figure 15 show the area - about 9 km² - in which, based on the current land use (rainfed permanent monocrop, *Vitis vinifera* L.) as CS9, the same diversification could be applied: vineyards intercropped with oregano (planted) for multiple uses. In the present situation (3 years of experiment in DF) there was an improvement in TOC, while after 30 years of such management no significant change is foreseen by the model. This option seems to be sustainable in both current and climate change situations. However, adjustment can be tested by modelling different options to improve the diversification in the long-term sustainability.

The maps in figure 16 show the same area with the current land use as CS9 in which the same diversification could be applied: vineyards intercropped with thymus (planted) for multiple uses. In the present situation (3 years of experiment in DF) there was an improvement in TOC, while after 30 years of such management no significant change is foreseen by the model. This option seems to be sustainable under current climate, but in the long term under climate change the diversification needs to be improved.

DIVERFARMING

Figure 16. Overview indicators maps for total organic carbon content of the Rheinland-Pfalz region at present time (a) and in the next 30 years (b), where the diversification option vineyards intercropped with thymus (planted) for multiple uses as CS9 is applied.

Hungary

Baranya region

Figure 17. Overview indicators maps for total organic carbon content of the Baranya region at present time (a) and in the next 30 years (b), where the diversification option vineyards intercropped with yarrow *Achillea millefolium* for industrial product (pharmacy) as CS11 is applied.

DIVERFARMING

The maps in figure 17 show the area - about 54 km² - in which, on the basis of the current land use as CS11 (rainfed permanent monocrop, *Vitis vinifera* L.), the same diversification could be applied: vineyards intercropped yarrow *Achillea millefolium* for industrial product (pharmacy). The area where no data are available was assumed to behave in the same way. In the present situation (3 years of experiment in DF) and after 30 years of such management predicted by the model there was an improvement in TOC due to the diversification compared to conventional systems. This option seems to be sustainable both in the immediate future with current climate and in the long term, under climate change.

The maps in figure 18 show the same area with the current land use as CS11 in which the same diversification could be applied: vineyards intercropped with native grass mix for fodder. In the present situation (3 years of experiment in DF) there was an improvement in TOC in 24% and a worsening in 76% of the considered area under current climate. This seems to be due to the different type of soils, acid and non-podzolic in the first case and Rendzina in the second case. After 30 years of such management, under climate change, a general improvement is foreseen by the model, thus this option seems to be sustainable in the long term.

DIVERFARMING

Figure 2. Overview indicators maps for total organic carbon content of the Baranya region at present time (a) and in the next 30 years (b), where the diversification option vineyards intercropped with native grass mix for fodder as CS11 is applied.

DIVERFARMING

Italy

Lombardy region

Figure 19. Overview indicators maps for total organic carbon content of the Lombardy region at present time (a) and in the next 30 years (b), where the diversification option tomato-pea/tomato-wheat as CS5 and CS7 is applied.

DIVERFARMING

The maps in figure 19 show the area - about 1243 km² – with the current land use as CS5 and CS7 (rainfed durum wheat and irrigated tomato), in which the same diversification could be applied: tomato-pea/tomato-wheat. In the present situation (3 years of experiment in DF) there was a reduction of TOC content, while after 30 years of such management a general improvement is foreseen by the model. The current reduction of C after the introduction in the rotation of a leguminous crop might be explained with the decrease of C/N ratio leading to higher organic matter degradation. This effect was registered also in other studies, but is generally transient. Despite of the bad performance of the proposed diversification in the current climate, it seems appropriate in the long term, under climate change, to increase the content of soil organic matter in the soil.

The maps in figure 20 show the same area with the current land use as CS5 and CS7 in which the same diversification could be applied: tomato-pea/tomato-wheat + digestate. In the present situation (3 years of experiment in DF) there was a general worsening in TOC content under current climate, while after 30 years of such management an improvement in 39% and a worsening in 61% of the considered area is foreseen by the model under climate change. This seems to be due to the different reaction of the two types of soils, Luvisols in the first case, Calcisols in the second case. This option could seem not sustainable in the immediate future, but can be appropriate in the long term - at least for Luvisols.

DIVERFARMING

Figure 3 Overview indicators maps for total organic carbon content of the Lombardy region at present time (a) and in the next 30 years (b), where the diversification option tomato-pea/tomato-wheat + digestate as CS5 and CS7 is applied. In figure (b) red polygons have the same soil characteristics of CS7, the green polygons those of CS5.

Spain

Huesca-Zaragoza region

Figure 21. Overview indicators maps for total organic carbon content of the Huesca-Zaragoza region at present time (a) and in the next 30 years (b), where the following diversification options are applied: barley monocropping with no tillage (211), pea-maize multiple cropping (212) and barley with no tillage (243).

DIVERFARMING

The maps in figure 21 show the areas with the same CORINE land use as CS3a (rainfed winter cereals, conventional monocropping - 211, about 4618 km²), CS3b (irrigated maize in monocropping - 212, about 2091 km²) and LT4 (rainfed barley - 243, about 1185 km²) in which the same diversifications could be applied: barley monocropping with no tillage (CS3a, 211), pea-maize multiple cropping (CS3b, 212) and barley with no tillage (LT4, 243). In the present situation (3 years of experiment in DF), under current climate, there was no significant change in TOC for 211 and an improvement for 212 and 243, while after 30 years of such management under climate change no significant change in TOC for 212 and an improvement for 211 and 243 is foreseen by the model. These options seem quite sustainable both in the immediate future and in the long term.

The maps in figure 22 show the same areas with the same CORINE land use as CS3a (211) and CS3b (212) in which the same diversifications could be applied: barley-wheat-pea rotation (CS3a, 211), and barley-maize multiple cropping (CS3b, 212). In the present situation (3 years of experiment in DF), under current climate, there was no significant change in TOC both for 211 and 212, while after 30 years of such management under climate change an improvement for 211 and no significant change for 212 is foreseen by the model. These options seem quite sustainable both in the immediate future and in the long term, but some adjustments can be done.

DIVERFARMING

Figure 22. Overview indicators maps for total organic carbon content of the Huesca-Zaragoza region at present time (a) and in the next 30 years (b), where the following diversification options are applied: barley-wheat-pea rotation (211), barley-maize multiple cropping (212).

Murcia region - Lorca municipality

Figure 23. Overview indicators maps for total organic carbon content of the Lorca region at present time (a) and in the next 30 years (b), where the diversification option almond monocrop with reduced tillage as LT3 is applied.

DIVERFARMING

The maps in figure 23 show the area - about 16 km² – with the same land use (almond orchard) as LT3, in which the same diversification could be applied: almond monocrop with reduced tillage. In the present situation (3 years of experiment in DF) under current climate there was no significant change in TOC, while after 30 years of such management under climate change an improvement is foreseen by the model. This option seems sustainable both in the immediate future and in the long term.

The maps in figure 24 show the same area with the current land use as LT3, in which the same diversification could be applied: almond intercropped with *Avena sativa* and *Vicia sativa* with reduced tillage. In the present situation (3 years of experiment in DF) under current climate there was no significant change in TOC content, while after 30 years of such management under climate change an improvement is foreseen by the model. This option seems to be sustainable both in the immediate future and in the long term.

DIVERFARMING

Figure 24. Overview indicators maps for total organic carbon content of the Lorca region at present time (a) and in the next 30 years (b), where the diversification option almond intercropped with *Avena sativa* and *Vicia sativa* with reduced tillage as LT3 is applied.

DIVERFARMING

Murcia municipality

Figure 25. Overview indicators maps for total organic carbon content of the Murcia municipality at present time (a) and in the next 30 years (b), where the following diversification options are applied: almond intercropped with *Capparis spinosa* as CS1 - in green in (a) + mandarin with cover crops (reduced tillage) intercropped with vetch/barley and fava bean as CS2 - in red in (a) (222), and melon in summer and leaf cabbage in winter - organic management as LT1 + melon with cowpea as CS16 (212).

DIVERFARMING

The maps in figure 25 show the areas with the same CORINE land use as CS1 and CS2 (rainfed conventional almond and irrigated conventional mandarins - 222, about 19 km²), and CS16 and LT1 (irrigated organic horticultural crops - 212, about 80 km²), in which the same diversifications could be applied: almond intercropped with *Capparis spinosa* (CS1, 222), mandarin with cover crops (reduced tillage) intercropped with vetch/barley and fava bean (CS2, 222), melon with cowpea (CS16, 212) and melon in summer and leaf cabbage in winter (organic management) (LT1, 212). In the present situation (3 years of experiment in DF) under current climate there was an improvement in TOC content for the diversification as CS1 (90% of the 222 area) and as CS16 (97% of the 212 area), no significant change in LT1 (3% of the 212 area) and a worsening for the diversification as CS2 (10% of the area). After 30 years of such management under climate change a worsening in TOC for CS16 (212) and an improvement for CS1, CS2 (222) and LT1 (212) is foreseen by the model. These options seem quite sustainable both in the immediate future and in the long term, except for the diversification adopted in CS16 that should be further adjusted.

The maps in figure 26 show the same areas with the same land use as CS1 and CS2 (222), and CS16 and LT1 (212), in which the same diversifications could be applied: almond intercropped with *Thymus hyemalis* (CS1, 222), mandarin with cover crops (reduced tillage) intercropped with vetch/barley and fava bean (1st year), campion, purslane and cardoon (2nd year) and cowpea and rocket (3rd year) (CS2, 222), melon with mixed intercropping (CS16, 212) and melon in summer and leaf cabbage in winter (biodynamic) (LT1, 212). In the present situation (3 years of experiment in DF) under current climate there was a loss of TOC for the diversification as CS1 and CS2 (222) and an increase for the diversification as CS16 and LT1 (212). After 30 years of such management under climate change a general improvement in TOC is foreseen by the model for all the considered diversification options, that seem to be sustainable especially in the long term.

DIVERFARMING

Figure 26. Overview indicators maps for total organic carbon content of the Murcia municipality at present time (a) and in the next 30 years (b), where the following diversification options are applied: almond intercropped with *Thymus hyemalis* as CS1 + mandarin with cover crops (reduced tillage) intercropped with vetch/barley and fava bean (1st year), campion, purslane and cardoon (2nd year) and cowpea and rocket (3rd year) as CS2 (222), melon in summer and leaf cabbage in winter (biodynamic) as LT1, and melon with mixed intercropping as CS16 (212).

DIVERFARMING

Figure 27. Overview indicators maps for total organic carbon content of the Murcia municipality at present time (a) and in the next 30 years (b), where the following diversification options are applied: melon in summer and leaf cabbage in winter (biodynamic) as LT1, and melon and row intercropping 1:1 vegetable phase as CS16 (212).

DIVERFARMING

The maps in figure 27 show the same areas in which the same diversification as CS16 and LT1 (212) could be applied: melon and row intercropping 1:1 vegetable phase (CS16, 212) and melon in summer and leaf cabbage in winter (biodynamic) (LT1, 212). In the other areas there were no data available. In the present situation (3 years of experiment in DF) there was no change in TOC for both the diversifications, while after 30 years of such management a general improvement in TOC is foreseen by the model. These options seem sustainable especially in the long term.

The maps in figure 28 show the same areas with the same land use as CS16 (212), in which the same diversification could be applied: melon and row intercropping 2:1 vegetable phase (CS16, 212). In the other areas there were no data available. In the present situation (3 years of experiment in DF) under current climate there was an improvement in TOC, as well as after 30 years of such management under climate change, foreseen by the model. This option seems really sustainable both in the immediate future and in the long term.

DIVERFARMING

Figure 28. Overview indicators maps for total organic carbon content of the Murcia municipality at present time (a) and in the next 30 years (b), where the following diversification options are applied: melon and row intercropping 2:1 Vegetable phase as CS16 (212).

DIVERFARMING

4. Conclusions

The results of this study confirm that a spatial assessment with maps both at field and at landscape scale can help stakeholders to get an overview at a glance on the impact of crop diversification management on farms and on the territory, and to identify issues and opportunities for crop diversification in improving sustainable management towards a more resilient agriculture.

The produced maps show the effect of the diversification tested in DF, considering two periods: the present, that is the time span of the DF experiments, and 30 years onward, predicted by the model. In particular, landscape maps individuate the territory with the same climatic, soil and land use characteristics of DF experimental areas, where it is possible to apply the same diversifications and possibly have the same results – showed in terms of worsening, no change and improvement of the indicators in comparison with the conventional management. Most of the studied diversification options resulted advantageous for soil health, depending on soil types and climate conditions; where the response were not positive the chosen diversification options probably need a longer time to produce positive effects, or some adjustment is necessary in the management strategy to best fit the pedo-climatic conditions of the area.

In this study a main barrier was identified at European level, that is the lack of soil profile data for large areas, not available and not homogeneous for all the Member States. Overcoming this issue is an aim of the European Joint Programme for Soil, thus in the future the applicability of the methods proposed in this project for upscaling crop diversification information at landscape level will be largely effective.

5. References

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